

ARTICULATING NARRATIVE CULTURAL HISTORY MODEL IN PLUNTURAN COMMUNITY, PONOROGO

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Abstract

The development of the history of the Indonesian nation, cultural history can be seen as an idea that has been marginalized from the academic world. This phenomenon means that this nation does not have sufficient knowledge to trace records and events that occurred in the past. Indonesian cultural history is considered uninteresting for cultural actors and critics, especially cultures with limited locality. In this research, the author wants to try to find a model for compiling a creative cultural historical narrative that occurred in a village that has the resources of historical actors and is still implementing it today. The fundamental object of cultural history in this research is to recognize the way social actors give meaning to their practices and discourse. The researcher therefore hopes to find in the tension between the inventive capacities of individuals or communities, On the other hand, there are constraints, standards and conventions that limit – more or less strictly according to the position they occupy in their relations of domination – what they may think, express, and do. Furthermore, this relationship is a reflection of broader societal attitudes, information professionals have been limited in their interpretation of photographs, social discourse, informant statements and cultural displays of art as historical evidence beyond the subject content of the image. It is hoped that the transcription of the informants' statements will provide a way to interpret cultural historical evidence more validly. The information that images provide to their viewers and their capacity to evoke the past have made them increasingly recognized as source material for the study of the history of this culture. This research draws on data sources and analysis materials from the village community of Plunturan District, Pulung District. Ponorogo will be used as a model in compiling cultural history. It is hoped that the results of this research can become a reference in compiling cultural history throughout Indonesia. The data used are not limited to the substantive structure of cultural works but also include gender and creative histories postulated collectively to provide an understanding of how events, social structures, and fundamental elements of social existence such as language, politics, and ideas about identity are formulated in a cultural timeline. in a certain historical period.

Keywords :**History; Culture; Transcription; Model; Substance**

INTRODUCTION

In the narrated histories of individual lives, it is not surprising to encounter elements of local or regional – or even national and international – history. After all, most of the narrated events that make up an individual's life history actually occur in physical locations where many other people's lives are also acted out, as well as various types of public events (1). Some such events, more or less external to the narrator of the individual life history, seem to have an extraordinary significance that makes it impossible to mention a particular place at a particular time without connecting these dominant units in one way or another. Some of these dominant units have a tendency to reappear in the life histories of several individuals of approximately the same age and from the same local community, thereby achieving the role of building stones in the construction of locally narrated cultural heritage (2).

Writing history is not just stringing a bunch of historical "facts" together in some kind of chronological order. It is the process of forming known facts into a coherent whole, which explains cause and effect and addresses the broader meaning or impact of an event (3). In other words, history as an academic discipline is an interpretive craft. Historians are not so much interested in describing a static picture of something or someone in the past, but rather in tracing how things changed over time (4).

Writing history involves answering "historical questions." These questions may ask why an event happened, who or what caused it, why it happened when it happened, or what its impact was (5). It may also discuss how a situation or institution changes over time. The important thing to remember is that writing history does not only explain what happened, but also why it happened. There is no single historical narrative. Every event involves multiple perspectives. Even if we knew every possible fact about past events, there would still be room for debate about how those facts fit together. Moreover, the surviving evidence has never been comprehensive (6). While extant documents—letters, diaries, newspapers, interviews, photographs, maps, government documents, etc.—may provide some information about an event, they cannot put us inside the minds of every participant. And in many cases few of these sources exist at all. Historical writing consists of two main types: primary source-based and secondary source-based (7). Primary sources are sources that are contemporary with the events being studied; for example, newspapers, letters, court records, or historical records based on interviews with actual participants involved in the event. Secondary sources, which include history textbooks, are books and articles written after the event. This does not include memoirs or other accounts written by participants in the event. That is, it is considered a primary source. Material culture refers to the physical objects, resources, and spaces that people use to define their culture. These include homes, neighborhoods, cities, schools, churches, synagogues, temples, mosques, offices, factories and plants, tools, means of production, goods and products, shops, and so on (8). All of these physical aspects of a culture help define the behavior and perceptions of its members.

Non-material culture refers to the nonphysical ideas people have about their culture, including beliefs, values, rules, norms, morals, language, organizations,

and institutions. For example, the non-material cultural concept of religion consists of a set of ideas and beliefs about God, worship, morals, and ethics. These beliefs, then, determine how a culture responds to its religious topics, issues, and events (9). When considering non-material culture, cultural historians refer to some of the processes that a culture uses to shape the thoughts, feelings, and behavior of its members. The four most important of these are symbols, language, values, and norms.

Symbols in the human mind are cultural representations of reality. Each culture has its own set of symbols associated with different experiences and perceptions. Thus, as representations, the meaning of symbols is neither instinctive nor automatic (10). Members of a culture must interpret and over time reinterpret the symbols. Symbols appear in many forms: verbal or nonverbal, written or unwritten. It can be anything that conveys meaning, such as words on a page, pictures, drawings, and gestures. Clothes, houses, cars, and other consumer goods are symbols that imply a certain level of social status.

The problems of this research include the following activities:

1. To identify and reveal the historical construction of cultural products built by residents of Plunturan village, Pulung District, Kab. Ponorogo.
2. To recognize social facts in the creation of culture in the village community of Plunturan District. Pulung, Ponorogo District, through arts performances in the village.
3. To identify the manifestation and classification of cultural products that appear in the Plunturan village community.
4. To build a cultural historical foundation for cultural products along with the background surrounding the process of their creation in Plunturan village.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied in this research is interdisciplinary, namely a methodology that tries to identify certain problems from the perspective of cultural history and other cultural studies. This method and approach brings historical phenomena closer to the interdisciplinary domain of cultural studies. Apart from the main disciplines of sociology and anthropology, other generative frameworks for providing an agenda for data analysis lie in the discipline of cultural history, while cultural sociology, cultural geography and new historicism are in literary studies. Engagement with history is like gaining experience of the sacred, the secular and the mundane or popular.

The method we use can be called an experimental genetic method in the sense that empirical facts will give rise to and create a genetic process of mental development whose main task of analysis is to return the process to its initial initial stage, or, in other words, turn something into a process (11). Experiments of this kind try to reveal every psychological form and deception and help turn them into interpretations and records of events flowing from separate, succeeding examples. In short, the problem of such an analysis can be reduced to taking each higher form of behavior not as a thing, but as a process and inserting it into motion so as not to proceed from the thing and its parts, but from a process to separate historical facts, sources and phenomena. The requirement

for experimental research is the necessity to reveal the original form of each mental function, a clear and open form of social relations. Every source, both written and spoken texts, occupies a higher role. The idea of representation is central to current cultural history. The concept of representation has come a long way to define cultural values, practices and assets. is concerned with "the basis of implicit rules that individuals experience while performing the roles assigned to them in the appropriation of cultural forms. The study of representation" has become very popular among cultural historians since the idea of representation began to reflect not only reality but also construct it. The schematic depiction of the methodology carried out in this research is as depicted in the infographic diagram below. Starting with ideas written in a research proposal, then the author attempts to explore historical traces in the Plunturan village community by looking for socio-cultural facts and conducting interviews with sources and confirming all the information obtained to be interpreted and examined in discussion and analysis with experts and competent sources.

RESEARCH METHODS
"MODEL OF PREPARATION OF HISTORICAL NARRATIVE OF CREATIVE CULTURE IN PLUNTURAN VILLAGE COMMUNITY KEC. PULUNG KAB. PONORAGO"

The development of popular interests depends on how history is represented. involves activities that atone for the past. The ongoing process of diverse interactions "between now and then is crucial to the study of culture because history provides" a series of resource pathways for constructing the past and representing the present. Complex forms of cultural history have concentrated on the materiality of memory, on the preservation, restoration and interpretation

of heritage sites. Interpretation, explanation and examination are carried out to form "individual and other collective identities (12). Facts, material objects and places play an important role in perpetuating and constructing collective historical cultural identities. Historical evidence, as well as historians' own accounts of the past, must be understood as representations , not a reconstruction of reality. As important forms of representation, "memory and other lived experiences share an intimate relationship with the capacity to change the present and the future (13). Basic and general knowledge can be "understood as a particular form of activity in a structured environment, which results in interaction with individuals or members of a group. This study advocates a view of culture as a complex phenomenon with socially produced and socially determined values that are valued by individuals or groups of individuals who engage in forms of practice. Cultural artifacts such as those we consider here act as mediating devices in that they imply a system and systems. it's embedded in the culture. Through repetition of practices through ritual, economic, heritage media (9). And by acquiring "a common cultural background, these institutions share a common and collective memory and identity that is understood through their various sociocultural forms in practice.

FACTS OF CULTURAL HISTORY

The origin of the word History is associated with the Greek word 'Historia' which means 'information' or 'investigation designed to obtain the truth'. History is the analysis and interpretation of the human past that allows us to study the continuity and changes that occur over time. It is an act of investigation and imagination seeking to explain how people have changed over time. Historians use all forms of evidence to examine, interpret, revisit, and reinterpret the past. This includes not only written documents, but also oral communications and objects such as buildings, artifacts, photographs, and paintings.

Historians trained in the methods of finding and evaluating these sources and their histories make it a challenging task to understand the history of them. History is a means of understanding past and present. Different interpretations of the past allow us to see the present differently and therefore imagine—and work toward—a different future. Often said to be the "queen" or "mother" of the social sciences. It is the basis of all subjects falling under the category of Humanities and Social Sciences. It is also the basis for the study of philosophy, politics, economics and even art and religion. No wonder, it is considered an indispensable subject in a complete human education.

Modern history has transcended its traditional status as antiquity and leisure pursuits a very useful and indispensable part of human education. It is more scientific and more comprehensive. This has expanded in all directions both vertically and horizontally. It has to be broad-based and interesting. According to modern concepts, history contains not only the history of kings and queens, battles and generals, but the common history of man-his home and clothing, his fields and cultivation, his constant efforts to protect his home and hearth, and to obtain a just government, his ideals. goals, achievements, disappointments, defeats and failures. This does not only happen to individuals, but also to communities and society. Society is the subject of historical study. Historical

studies deepen our understanding of the potential and limitations that exist today. Thus, it has become a future-oriented study dealing with present-day problems. For all these reasons, history has assumed the role of human science.

1. History is the study of humans: History is concerned with human struggles over the centuries. History is not static. By selecting “countless biographies” and presenting their lives in appropriate social contexts and ideas in human contexts, we understand the sweep of events. It traces the fascinating story of how humans have developed over the centuries, how humans have learned to use and control their environment and how the institutions that exist today grew out of the past.
2. History deals with humans in time: History deals with a series of events and each event occurs at a particular point in time. Human history is actually a process of human development in time. It is a time that provides perspective on events and provides an illuminating charm to the past.
3. History is concerned with humans in space: Human interaction with the environment and its vices in turn is a dynamic one. History describes nations and human activities in the world in the context of their physical and geographical environment. From here emerge various trends in the political, social, economic and cultural fields of human activity and achievements.
4. Objective event record: Every precaution is taken to base the data on original data sources and make it free from subjective interpretation. This helps in clear understanding of the past and enables us to take the right decisions.
5. Many-sided: All aspects of the life of a social group are closely interrelated and are historical. The events that occur cover all aspects of life, not limited to just the political aspect, which has dominated history for a long time.
6. History is a dialogue between past and future events that increasingly develops to an end. The historian's interpretation of the past, his selection of important matters and relevant events, develops as new goals progressively emerge. The general laws governing historical events may not be considered sufficient; efforts should be made to predict future events based on the law.
7. Not only narrative but also analysis: The selected events are not simply narrated; the causal relationships between them are properly explored. This tracing of relationships leads to the development of general laws which are also compared and contrasted with similar occurrences in other social groups to increase the reliability and validity of these laws.
8. Continuity and coherence are essential conditions in history: History carries the burden of human progress passed down from generation to generation, from society to society, confirming the essence of continuity.
9. Relevant: In historical studies only the events listed are relevant to History's understanding of current life.
10. Completeness: According to modern concepts, history is not limited to one period or country or nation. It also deals with all aspects of human

life-political, social, economic, religious, literary, aesthetic and physical, providing a clear sense of world unity and world citizenship.

FUNCTION OF CULTURAL HISTORY

Cultural history brings past times and places to life. In this pursuit, cultural historians study beliefs and ideas, as do intellectual historians. In addition to the writings of the intellectual elite, they also considered the (sometimes unwritten) ideas of disadvantaged and less educated groups. This is reflected in deliberately artistic cultural products, but also includes objects and experiences of everyday life, such as clothing or cuisine. "Culture" can also mean everyday attitudes, values, assumptions and prejudices, as well as the rituals and practices that express them, ranging from magical beliefs to gender roles and racial hierarchies. In this sense, our instincts, thoughts, and actions have ancestors that can be scrutinized and critically examined by cultural history.

Cultural history is an attempt to inhabit the minds of people from different worlds. This journey, like any great work of literature, is also thrilling. It is also valuable to reflect on our own historical moments. Like the air we breathe, the cultural context that shapes our understanding of the world is often invisible to those around us; Cultural history allows us to take a step back, and realize that some of what we take for granted is extraordinary, and that some of what we consider unchangeable and natural is contingent and open to change. Studying how mental categories have changed inspires us to think about how our culture and society might evolve, and to ask what we can do as individuals to shape that process.

CULTURAL HISTORY IN PLUNTURAN

A primary source is any original source – an image, text, newspaper article, political cartoon, map, deed, letter, diary, or artifact; and the list goes on and on - commenting on, testifying to, or bearing witness to the time period of its own production. In this case, primary sources are historical raw materials. These events are what historians study when they try to learn what happened in the past, and what an event meant in the context of its time. Primary sources provide direct or direct information about a topic, event, object, person, or work of art from people who have a direct relationship with it. People who witness these events within a certain period of time as participants or observers, write or produce direct experiences of a topic, an event. Primary sources can be written or unwritten such as video recordings, postcards.

Primary Sources are Historians encounter a wide variety of sources during their studies. There are, of course, basic textbooks - usually collaborative efforts by several established historians, well illustrated with maps, charts, graphs, photographs, artwork, and more.

Original documents (birth certificates, property deeds, trial transcripts, court records, agreements, official or unofficial organizational papers, bills)

1. Autobiography and memoir
2. Diaries, personal letters, and speeches -- what the people involved said or wrote

3. Interviews, surveys and fieldwork, statistics, scientific journal articles with experimental results
4. Internet communication via email, blogs, video and audio recordings that capture events
5. Photos, drawings and posters
6. Works of art and literature, clothing, furniture, kitchen staff
7. Books, magazines and newspaper articles published at the time
8. Public opinion poll
9. Speeches and oral history
10. Paten
11. Technical report
12. Newspaper reports, by journalists who witnessed an event or quoted people who witnessed it.

Secondary sources are created by someone who does not directly experience or participate in the event or condition. They may cover the same topics as primary sources but they describe, discuss, interpret, comment on, analyze, evaluate, summarize first-hand accounts meaning primary sources. Through generalization, synthesis, interpretation, commentary or evaluation, secondary sources aim to convince readers of the author's argument. Secondary sources also provide research bibliographies and notes on primary sources.

According to Michael J. Galgano, Secondary sources provide historians, both experienced and novice, with two very important types of information: secondary sources are useful in providing background information about a topic and they help provide historical context. Types of secondary sources include:

1. Journal articles that comment on or analyze research
2. Textbooks that interpret or analyze primary sources
3. Dictionaries and encyclopedias
4. Political commentary
5. Biography
6. dissertation
7. Newspaper editorial
8. Criticism and commentary on literature, works of art or music

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

In connection with writing the history of culture in Plunturan, there are folktales, cultural products, and historical sites discovered which can be used as sources for writing the cultural history of Plunturan. There are also social organization, heritages and villagers pioneer that can reveal what happened with the society. Since the ancestors began living established their lives in Plunturan, housing has become a basic need in human life. Initially, settlements were built with the aim of meeting physical needs. However, in its development, the selection and ownership of settlements has been entitled with certain terms such as Krajan, Cabean, Gadungan, Suru as they are developed for psychological, aesthetic, social status and economic needs. While certain landscape are named by legendaries that following the location, such as sekebo, sepilang, kedunglumbu, mbanaran, satariman.

History of culture in this village is also dominated with the existence of performance arts, namely Reyog, Jathilan, Ponoragan, Klana Sewandana Dance, Obyog, gajah gajahan. Those are a constellation of arts that become cultural indicators constructed by the villagers. Since good research and good writing go hand in hand, perhaps the single most important key to research success is having a good topic. For that, what you need up front are two things: (a) a problem you're really interested in and (b) specific issues, controversies, techniques, instruments, people, etc. which may offer a useful path forward to explore your problem. In the early stages, it's often a good idea to be very general about (a) and very specific about (b). So you might be interested in why people decide to become doctors, and decide to look at the early career of a practitioner from the early nineteenth century, when the evidence for this kind of question is surprisingly good. You can get a lot of advice from people in the Department about where to look for topics, especially if you combine it with reading in areas of potential interest. Remember that you are more likely to get good advice if you are able to combine your interests with something the potential supervisor knows. HPS is such a vast field that it is impossible for any single department to cover all aspects of it with an equivalent level of expertise. Knowing that your topic will evolve as your research progresses can be reassuring, although it is important that you establish some basic parameters relatively quickly. Otherwise, you will end up doing research for two, three, or even four research papers or dissertations, when all you need is the material for one research paper.

Before starting any detailed work, it's a good idea to read some secondary literature surrounding your subject. More general books are listed in the reading list for Part II courses, and some specialized literature is listed in this research guide. This doesn't need to involve in-depth searching, at least not at this stage, but you do need to master the basics of what has been done if you want to be able to assess the relevance of whatever you find. If there are lectures offered in your topic, be sure to attend them; and if it's offered later in the year, see if you can get a preliminary bibliography from the professor.

After that, it's usually a good idea to immerse yourself in your main primary sources as soon as possible. If you're studying a museum piece, now's the time to take a closer look; if you are writing about a debate, collect the main papers relevant to the debate and read them carefully; if you are writing about a particular experiment, look at published papers, laboratory notebooks, and relevant letters. Don't spend hours in the early stages of research finding hard-to-find details, unless you are absolutely sure that those details are critical to the viability of your topic. Start to get a feel for the material you have, and questions that might be explored further. Make an outline of the main topics you want to cover, organized by the themes you find most interesting (and remember, 'background' is usually not an interesting theme).

At this stage, research can go in many directions. At some point, you'll want to read more about the techniques other historians use to explore similar questions. Most fields have established ways of dealing with problems, and you need to know what those ways are, especially if you decide to reject them. One of the advantages of an interdisciplinary field like HPS is that you are exposed

to different and often conflicting ways of approaching similar questions. Remember that this applies to history itself, and you need to know the alternatives. This may require searching further afield, in classic books or articles that do not specifically cover 'your' subject. For example, you might be able to find some useful ideas for studying modern scientific portraiture in a book about the eighteenth century. The best book related to educational maps may not be the astronomy book you are studying, but the book used to teach classical geography. See where the inspiration for the work you admire came from, and see the sources they used. This will help you develop the types of focused questions that produce successful work.

As you develop an outline and begin to think about your topic in more detail, you will be in a good position to plan possible research paths. Don't try to find out everything about your topic: choose the aspects that may prove most beneficial to the direction your essay is headed. For example, it may be worth spending a long time looking for details of someone's biography if their career and life are important to your analysis; but in many other cases, such issues may not be that important.

The essence of historical analysis is to analyze the various cause-and-effect relationships present in each scenario, taking into account the ways in which individuals, influential ideas, and different thought patterns interact and influence each other. It's about figuring out what facts combine to form a coherent story, which helps us understand ourselves and others better. But such understanding, or what is considered "coherent," can change with each generation. That's where you and your interests as a student of history come into play. An important key to this discipline is that our analysis of an event or individual is tentative or ephemeral. The historian's job is to study the available evidence and form meaningful conclusions; therefore, as new evidence and perspectives (including yours!) emerge, they may change our understanding of the past.

Some things change, some things stay the same—the story isn't that interesting but it's worth worrying about because history, as the best teachers will tell you, is about telling stories. Good storytelling, we think, is built on an understanding of context. Given the younger generation's fascination with narrative and their enthusiasm for imaginative play, students (especially elementary school students) often find context the most interesting element in historical thinking. As students get older, of course they realize that the past is not just a fun alternate universe. Working with primary sources, they found that the past made more sense when they placed it within two frameworks. This kind of context determines the situation; the second helps us interpret evidence about subsequent actions. Texts, events, individual lives, collective struggles—all develop in a tightly knit world.

Historians use context, change over time, and causality to form arguments that explain changes in the past. Although scientists can design experiments to test theories and produce data, historians cannot change past conditions to produce new information. Instead, they must base their arguments on interpretations of partial primary sources that often provide multiple explanations for a single event. Uncertainty will trouble some parties, but the historical space is at its most dynamic when sources encourage researchers to

evaluate the contribution of various factors in shaping past events, and formulate arguments that emphasize the superiority of some causes over others. If your interest is in the reception of a work, it would be more beneficial to learn a lot about a few comments or reviews (where the work appeared, who wrote it, and so on) than to collect all the comments at random. can find. Follow up on instructions in other people's footnotes. Works that are boring or outdated in approach are sometimes based on very solid research. A single secondary reference to an important letter or newspaper article can save hours of searching, and lead you directly to the information you need. Additionally, good historians often flag questions or sources that they feel are worthy of further investigation.

Remember that the best history almost always depends on developing new approaches and interpretations, not on knowledge of secret archives that no one has used before. If the Researcher gives the Researcher's work time to develop, and combines research with writing, the Researcher will discover new sources, and (even better) the importance of new material that has supposedly been known for a long time. Once the Researcher becomes familiar with the Researcher's topic, the Researcher will likely discover that the evidence the researcher unearthed at the start of the project is much more important than what is presented in the current historical record. In historical research, the most important evidence often does not just appear out of thin air – it is something the researcher needs to unearth through careful reading and understanding of the circumstances in which the document the researcher is studying was written, or where the object was located. produced. This is especially true for instruments, paintings and other non-textual sources.

At first glance, writing about history seems like an overwhelming task. The subject of history is very broad, covering all human affairs in the recorded past -until the present, that is, the researcher begins to read this guide. Since no one person can consult all these records, no work of history can pretend to be so comprehensive or universal. At the same time, the subject matter of History is partly irretrievable. Except for the discovery of time travel, no scholar has been able to experience or recreate the past directly under laboratory conditions. Historians must rely on the fragmentary records that survive from the time period being studied, which of course reveal only part of the story.

For these reasons, the guiding principles behind all historical writing must be selection and interpretation: a judicious selection of topics and questions that seem most interesting, and a responsible interpretation of sources to build a meaningful argument. Subjective decisions about what to include, what not to include, and how to understand it make writing history easy. No less important, they also managed to be controversial, because scholars certainly disagreed with the assessments of other scholars. Researchers can think of historical writing, then, as an ongoing argument or debate regarding this unavoidable process of selection and interpretation. The researcher's first challenge as a writer must be to find a way to enter this conversation.

Some histories are narrative (organized like a story according to chronology, or sequence of events), and others are analytical (organized like an essay according to the internal logic of the topic). Some papers are concerned with

history (not just what happened, of course, but why and how it happened), and others are interested in historiography (that is, how other historians have written history, especially the particularities of different works, scholars, or schools of thought). Some papers emphasize social or cultural history, others political or military history, and many more intellectual or economic history (or other genres). In an undergraduate program, it is likely that the Researcher will see a difference between a review essay (often based on the Researcher's responses to assigned readings from the course syllabus) and a research paper (usually requiring additional research in a library or archive on a topic of the Researcher's own choosing). Different types of History papers naturally require a certain amount of research, analysis, and interpretation. Despite their diversity, historical arguments often assume a general form. If the Researcher has difficulty developing an argument for the Researcher's paper, the Researcher will follow rhetorical steps (see next section). Think of this approach as a ready-to-wear outfit that the Researcher can try on and adapt to the needs of the Researcher's assignment. After the researcher decides on an argument that can be applied, state the researcher's readers clearly and concisely in prose regarding this research problem. The initial statement of this research is presented in the opening of a shorter essay or the opening section of a longer paper.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion in this study the researcher can draw the interpretation that history is often criticized for its tendency to privilege "normal" behavior, its excessive reliance on static structures, and in categorizing individuals into predetermined groups. In replacing social history as the dominant new perspective on the past, cultural historians attempted to answer some of the serious questions that arose about the methods of social historians as they adopted the new subjects that social historians had brought to the field. In their revised strategy, cultural historians brought back to consciousness issues related to the contingent, the personal, and the eccentric. At the same time, in moving away from the robust research methods and forms of disciplinary inquiry that have become the hallmarks of social historians, cultural historians have often become embroiled in problems that have now become highly visible in the field. By urging that the close link between cultural and social history be renewed.

However, the use of the above method shows limitations that cannot be overcome simply by enriching the data set used. That approach is both misleading and enlightening. This tends to indicate a mechanical relationship between cultural context and people's ways of acting. This does not explain the processes through which culture profoundly influences ways of acting without determining those ways. At the same time, efforts to reduce the value of culture in the formation of history become more important and enable researchers to compare the value of each culture in historical records. This makes it possible to understand the relationships between those who have different cultural references. It is especially challenging to see these relationships as shaped by

some kind of death, ignoring the room for maneuver that the protagonists can exploit to find an appropriate mode of operation.

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